

Organophosphoryl Ethanamine Analogues

III. Synthesis of N, N-Dimethylphosphoramidic Acid Esters

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A series of phosphoramidic acid esters having the general structure (I) has been prepared as potential anticholinestras agents. In this series X equals O or S. The compounds were prepared in a single vessel, in good yield.

THE anticholinestras are widely used in medicine¹ and in agriculture as insecticides²⁻⁶. The most toxic derivatives are used as warfare agents⁷. In the course of our studies on the synthesis of organophosphates acting as anticholinestras by irreversible inactivity of the enzyme cholinestrase⁸, it was of interest to determine how various substituents on the phosphorus atom affect the electrophilicity of the phosphoryl group which would in turn affect the physiological activity. This paper describes the synthesis of the phosphoramidic acid esters (I), by a very simple method involving the condensation of phosphoramidic dichloride (II) with alcohols, to give the chlorides (III), the latter in turn was treated *in situ* with 2-tertiary-aminoethanol to yield (I). This is shown in the following scheme :

The infrared spectra of all the compounds were recorded as thin films, using a sodium chloride window on a spectromom 2000 infrared spectrometer. The infrared data indicated that all the compounds exhibit a sharp band around 1300 cm^{-1} , (P=O), and two bands at about 1020 and 770 cm^{-1} due to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibration of the P-N-C group respectively. However, the 1020 cm^{-1} band may be due to P-O-C (alkyl).⁹

Because of their expected physiological properties, a study for their biological effects will be made and the results will be reported in due time.

Experimental

General procedure for the preparation of phosphoramidic acid esters (1-16) :

A mixture of 0.1 mol of the appropriate alcohol and 0.1 mol of triethylamine in 200 ml dry benzene was placed in a 500 ml round bottomed, three-necked flask fitted with a mechanical stirrer, dropping funnel and a condenser. The mixture was cooled down to $5-10^\circ$. To the cold mixture 0.1 mol of N,N-dimethylamino-phosphoramidic dichloride dissolved in 100 ml dry benzene was added with stirring at such a rate keeping the reaction temperature below 10° . A white precipitate of triethylamine hydrochloride was separated during the addition. The reaction mixture was stirred at room

temperature for another 2 hours. To this a mixture, 0.1 mol of 2-tertiaryaminoethanol or thioethanol and 0.1 mol of triethylamine in 100 ml dry benzene was added dropwise with stirring. Upon completion of the addition the temperature was gradually raised. Heating and stirring was continued for further 3 hours, keeping the temperature between $60-70^\circ$. This mixture was allowed to cool at room temperature. Triethylamine hydrochloride, separated as white precipitate, was filtered and washed with 100 ml of dry benzene. The solvent was then removed and the residue was distilled under vacuum. The physical data are summarized in table 1.

No.	X	Y	R	R'	b. p. °C/mm. Hg	n _D ²⁰	d ₄ ²⁰	Molecular formula	Microanalysis (%)					
									Calculated			Found		
									C	H	N	C	H	N
1	O	Y ₁	-C ₂ H ₅	-C ₂ H ₅	97-98/5	1.4342	0.8390	C ₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ P	45.37	9.73	11.76	45.29	9.63	11.23
2	O	Y ₁	-C ₂ H ₇ (n)	-C ₂ H ₇ (n)	63/0.6	1.4315	0.8372	C ₁₁ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₂ P	49.61	10.22	10.52	49.62	10.09	10.50
3	O	Y ₁	-CH ₃	-C ₆ H ₅	97-99/0.4	1.5160	0.9741	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ P	52.93	7.77	10.29	52.87	7.73	10.32
4	O	Y ₂	-C ₂ H ₅	-C ₂ H ₅	85-86/3	1.4287	0.8381	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ P	47.61	9.99	11.10	47.55	9.92	10.87
5	O	Y ₂	-C ₂ H ₇ (n)	-C ₂ H ₇ (n)	92-93/5	1.4330	0.8572	C ₁₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ P	51.41	10.43	9.99	51.38	10.08	9.88
6	O	Y ₂	-CH ₃	-C ₆ H ₅	128/4	1.4978	0.9921	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₂ P	54.54	8.1	9.78	54.51	8.12	9.63
7	O	Y ₂	-C ₂ H ₅	-C ₂ H ₅	62-63/1.4	1.4357	0.8442	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ P	49.61	10.22	10.52	49.57	10.20	10.49
8	O	Y ₂	-C ₂ H ₇ (n)	-C ₂ H ₇ (n)	53-55/0.6	1.4290	0.8605	C ₁₃ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ P	53.04	10.61	9.52	53.18	10.54	9.51
9	O	Y ₂	-CH ₃	-C ₆ H ₅	108-110/2	1.4560	1.1320	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ P	55.99	8.39	9.33	55.87	8.32	9.33
10	O	Y ₄	-C ₂ H ₅	-C ₂ H ₅	90-91/10	1.4532	0.9371	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ P	50.00	9.53	10.60	49.87	9.54	10.62
11	O	Y ₄	-C ₂ H ₇ (n)	-C ₂ H ₇ (n)	102-103/10	1.4462	0.9284	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ P	53.41	10.00	9.58	53.37	9.98	9.55
12	O	Y ₄	-CH ₃	-C ₆ H ₅	122-123/5	1.5344	1.1514	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ P	56.37	7.77	9.39	56.21	7.69	9.37
13	S	Y ₁	-C ₂ H ₅	-C ₂ H ₅	110-112/3	1.4585	0.9838	C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ PS	42.50	9.12	11.01	42.52	9.11	11.00
14	S	Y ₂	-C ₂ H ₅	-C ₂ H ₅	82-83/1	1.4735	0.8482	C ₁₀ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ PS	44.76	9.39	10.44	45.74	9.37	10.42
15	S	Y ₂	-C ₂ H ₅	-C ₂ H ₅	68-70/0.2	1.4560	0.9545	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ PS	46.79	9.64	9.92	46.82	9.69	9.91
16	S	Y ₄	-C ₂ H ₅	-C ₂ H ₅	87-88/1	1.4621	0.9371	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ PS	47.12	8.99	9.99	47.20	8.98	9.97

Y₁ = -OCH₂; Y₂ = -OC₂H₅; Y₃ = -C₂H₇ (iso); Y₄ = -OCH₂-CH=CH₂.

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